

INVESTIGATING UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' MOTIVATION TOWARDS ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract:

This research aims at investigating the motivational factors of university students towards English Language learning. A quantitative method using a descriptive design was recommended for this study. A questionnaire was used as the data collection tool. The population comprises all males and females third-year English language learners at colleges of education and languages at Sudan University of Science and Technology. Thus, the researcher used a sample size of 100 English language learners at colleges of Education and languages in Sudan University of Science and Technology being selected as participants in the current study, 99 valid responses were collected. Collected data is entered and treated by using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The following are some of the important findings based on data analysis and discussion of the collected data: 1. Many factors have a positive effect on students' attitudes and motivation to learn the English language. The most important ones include, having a good English language teacher positively affects their attitudes to learn English, and Learning English is important, as it is one of the requirements for high- education. 2. Students were highly motivated to learn the English language. There are many factors, motivate the students, on top of the motivates factors is that, the need for traveling around the world, and the second motivator is that, almost all students confirm that, learning English makes them more knowledgeable as they can be able to communicate. Finally, the results of the study, do not detect any statistically significant variations between students of the current study perceptions regarding learning the English language related to students' gender and age.

Keywords: motivation, English language learning

1. Introduction

One thing that students, teachers, material developers, and researchers all agree upon is that motivation is an essential factor that affects the rate and success of second or foreign language learning. As an English language teacher, I'm certainly concerned with the motivational issue of my students in learning English. Motivation is often considered as one of the main elements that determine success in foreign or second language learning. According to Girard (2005, p. 97) "*Motivation is such a basic factor in language learning that I cannot see how any teacher could avoid being concerned with his pupils' motivation.*" Motivation is certainly connected with language achievements in the sense language achievements cannot happen without motivation. To have an in-depth investigation of the relationship between motivation and achievement in foreign language learning in the department of English, College of Education and Languages in Sudan University of Science and Technology, some background needs to be considered first. This includes the socio-economic and socio-cultural backgrounds as they relate to English language learning in Sudan the current role and status of the English language in Sudan, the educational Systems, and the rationale of the research topic, the aims of the study and research questions supporting the current study as well as the overview of the thesis. The following sections will deal with all these aspects as will follow.

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

From her experiences in teaching English at the university level for many years. The researcher observed that university students aren't highly motivated towards English language learning.

In fact, that some students aren't aware enough of their reasons for learning English, they were only guided by their parents' desires. However, some are aware, so they do their best to improve their English skills to increase their knowledge and opportunities in getting a decent job when they graduate. For the above-mentioned reasons, the researcher aims to investigate the motivational and attitudinal factors of University students towards English Language learning.

1.3 Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are:

1. To classify difficulties, which emerge from the data, in the motivation of the University learners.
2. To provide general pedagogical implications to motivate University students toward learning English.
3. To investigate the university students' motivation for learning English.

1.4 Research Questions

1. To what extent are university students motivated towards learning the English language?

2. To what extent does the university students' background affect their motivation regarding English language learning?
3. What are the possible factors which determine the reasons for learning the English language?

2. Literature Review and Previous Studies

2.1 Definition of Motivation

Most researchers agree that motivation plays a vital role in the learner's achievement; it is often attributed to the capacity to override other factors that contribute to language learning. Although 'motivation' is a term repeatedly used in both educational and research contexts, it is rather surprising how little agreement there is in the literature with regard to the exact meaning of this notion? This variety is, of course, no accident; as Dörnyei (2014) points out, motivation theories, in general, seek to explain no less than the fundamental question of why humans behave as they do, and therefore it wouldn't be simple to take up any simple and direct answer. The levels and kinds of motivation in any individual are different from others. In other words, not only levels and amounts of motivation in individuals are different, but their kinds of motivation can be also different. Furthermore, motivation to learn an L2 presents a particularly complex and unique situation even within motivational psychology, due to the multifaceted nature and roles of language itself. Language is at the same time: (a) a communication coding system that can be taught as a school subject; (b) an integral part of the individual's identity involved in almost all mental activities; and also (c) the most important channel of the social organization embedded in the culture of the community where it is used. Therefore, the motivational basis of language attainment is not directly comparable to that of the mastery of other subject matters in that knowing an L2 also involves the development of some sort of 'L2 identity' and the incorporation of elements from the L2 culture (Gardner, 1985); thus, in addition to the environmental and cognitive factors normally associated with learning in current educational psychology, L2 motivation also contains featured personality and social dimensions.

In summary, L2 motivation is necessarily a multifaceted construct, and describing its nature and its core features requires particular care. Unfortunately, it happens that some researchers take the notion of motivation for granted and refers to it without specifying in what sense they use the term. Finally, Johnstone (1999, p. 146), considers motivation as a stimulant for achieving a specific target similarly, according to (Ryan & Deci, 2000). To be motivated means to progress or to be in motion to do something. While Ellis (1994, p. 715) considers motivation as the attempt which learners make for learning a second language because of "*their need or desire to learn it*".

Lightbrown and Spada (2001, p. 33) identified motivation in second language acquisition as "*a complex phenomenon which can be defined in terms of two factors: learners' communicative needs and their attitudes towards the second language community*". They believe that when learners think that they need to speak the second language to be in touch with

others or accomplish and achieving specialized and dedicated desires and goals, they will be stimulated and inspired to obtain expertise and skill in it.

Finally, as a researcher, I noticed that different people define motivation from different views and it may be due to the existence of different contexts of language learning, but the most important thing all of them agreed upon is that motivation is an important key factor to learning a language. So, in this study motivation is considered an important factor in the achievement of learning English as a second language.

2.2 Types of Motivation

2.2.1 Integrative and Instrumental Motivation

According to Gardner (2003), there are mainly two types of learning motivation: i.e., learning the language as an instrument to achieve practical goals, and, i.e., learning the language out of interest in or desire to identify with the target culture. We will take for example two different types of motivation, which according to Gardner (2003) is likely to be the two most important under the concept of motivation.

These two types of motivation can affect and control the procedure and outcome of learning. Cook (2000) further believes that the integrative and instrumental motivation suggested by Gardner and Lambert is a useful and effective factor for second language learning.

Gardner (1985) and Ellis (1994) also introduce the mentioned types of motivation; The former occurs when the student likes to join or be a member of the certain crowd and the culture. The latter crops up when the learner anticipates numerous benefits that he proposes to have while learning some particular language. Instrumental Motivation involves the perception of purely practical value in learning the L2, such as increasing occupational or business opportunities, enhancing prestige and power, accessing scientific and technical information, or just passing a course in school. Motivation has been identified as the learner's orientation concerning the goal of learning a second language (Crookes and Schmidt, 1991). It is thought that students who are most successful when learning a target language are those who like the people that speak the language, admire the culture and have a desire to become familiar with or even integrate into the society in which the language is used (Crookes and Schmidt, 1991). This form of motivation is known as integrative motivation. Comparing these two types of motivation with each other, Ellis (1994) believes that the best and the perfect motivation is integrative motivation. He believes that integrative motivation is more competent and well-organized. Students who don't have the instrumental or integrative motivation will face problems and difficulties to learn and gain knowledge of a second language in the classroom and generally, learning the language would be difficult for them (Cook, 2000).

2.2.2. Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation

The fundamental difference is between intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation is the eagerness and interest to do and take part in certain activities because an individual feel that they are attractive and pleasant. Students who have intrinsic motivation are inclined to stay with intricate and complicated problems and gain

knowledge from their slips and mistakes (Walker, et al., 2006). Besides, intrinsic motivation is essential and fundamental for the integration process through which elements of one's accessible internal awareness and knowledge is assimilated or mixed with new knowledge. Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is the propensity to take part in activities because of the reasons which do not link to the activity. These reasons can be the anticipation of reward or punishment, like being successful in the exam or getting a good mark (Pintrich, 2003) believe that "*intrinsic motivation refers to motivation to engage in an activity for its own sake*". People who are intrinsically motivated work on tasks because they find them enjoyable. Task participation is its own reward and does not depend on explicit rewards or other external constraints.

To sum up, intrinsic motivation is a motivation to do an activity because of itself. The individuals who are intrinsically motivated do and practice the activities and works because they feel that those activities are enjoyable. Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is motivation to do work or an activity as a means or way to achieve a target. Also, Pintrich (2003, pp.257-258) argued that extrinsic motivation is the motivation to engage in an activity as a means to an end. Individuals who are extrinsically motivated work on tasks because they believe that participation will result in desirable outcomes such as a reward, teacher praise or avoidance of punishment. Those who are extrinsically motivated perform and do affairs as they think that their contribution will cause enviable results like a reward, teacher admiration, or evasion (prevention) of punishment (Pintrich, 2003).

Gardner (1885) argues that intending to be motivated, the learner necessitates, requires, and needs to have something to anticipate, foresee, expect and long for, a reason, principle, or rationale having to do with aim or target. Concerning second/foreign language acquisition, this intention would be learning a foreign language. There must be something that the learner desires to achieve or do, being the target language the vehicle to attain it. According to Cook (2000), the performance and presentation of several learners in the context of second or foreign language learning is improved and superior to others. The reason is that they are better motivated. Ellis (1994) sees the incident of learning using motivation and believes that the learning process simply occurs when a person is motivated. Relating to this matter Ellis (1994, p. 508) says that "*language teachers readily acknowledge the importance of learners' motivation, not infrequently explaining their sense of failure concerning their students' lack of motivation*".

Cook (2000) believes that there are three main factors which influence the Second Language Learning These three factors are: age, personality, and motivation. Motivation is the most significant factor among the mentioned three factors that affect second language learning. Ellis (1994, p. 715) suggests that motivation is "*the effort which learners put into learning an L2 as a result of their need or desire to learn it*". Also, (Lightbrown and Spada 2001). Believe that when learners think that they need to speak the second language to be in touch with others or accomplish and achieving specialized desires and goals, they will be motivated to obtain expertise and skill in it.

2.3 Motivation and Language Learning

Motivation is one of the important aspects of second language learning. Motivation is a kind of desire for learning. It is very difficult to teach a second language in a learning environment if the learner does not have a desire to learn a language.

A. Language Learning Motivation (LLM)

Social psychologists were the first to initiate serious research on motivation in language learning because of their awareness of the social and cultural effects on L2 learning (Dörnyei, 2015). This interest was translated into the appearance of several models that stressed the affective aspect of language learning including (Krashen's, 1985) Monitor Model and Schumann's (1986) Acculturation Model.

However, the most influential model of LLM in the early sixties through the eighties of the previous century was developed by Gardner.

B. The Socio-educational Model (Gardner, 1985)

Gardner defined motivation as a *"combination of effort plus desire to achieve the goal of learning the language plus favorable attitudes towards learning the language"* (ibid:10). In his model, Gardner talked about two kinds of motivation, the integrative and the instrumental, with much emphasis on the former. The integrative motivation refers to learners' desire to at least communicate or at most integrate (or even assimilate) with the members of the target language. The instrumental motivation refers to more functional reasons for learning the language such as getting a better job, a higher salary or passing an examination (Gardner, 1985).

There are several components in the socio-educational model which are measured using different attitudinal and motivational scales in what Gardner called the AMBT (Attitude / Motivation Test Battery). Imperativeness is measured by three scales: attitudes towards the target language group, interest in foreign languages, and integrative orientation. Motivation is also measured by three scales: motivational intensity (the amount of effort invested in learning the language), attitudes toward learning the target language and the desire to learn the target language. Attitudes toward the learning situation which refer to the individual's reactions to anything associated with the immediate context in which learning takes place is measured by two scales: attitudes toward the teacher and attitudes toward the course.

However, it was the integrative motivation that was most stressed by Gardner and it was the backbone of his model. The role of attitudes towards the learned language, its speakers and the learning situation are all considered parts of the integrative motivation. The integrative aspect of the model appears in three different components: integrative orientation, Imperativeness, and integrative motivation. Gardner repeatedly stressed the differences among these components (Gardner 1985, 2001; Masgoret and Gardner, 2003) since confusion was often made between orientations and motivations. According to Gardner, orientation refers to the set of reasons for which an individual study the language; whereas, motivation refers to the driving force which involves expending effort, expressing desire and feel enjoyment. The term orientation is problematic since it

can also mean 'attitude or inclination'. Still, however, other understandings of the concept of orientation have been suggested. It is important to emphasize at this stage that LLM researchers called for expanding and rectifying the socio-educational model rather than degrading or eliminating it (Dörnyei, 2015)

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Methodology

Parahoo (2006, p. 12) claimed that to achieve the objectives and aims of the study it is essential for the researcher to choose the most suitable design for achieving the objectives of the study. A quantitative method using a descriptive design had recommended for this study. A questionnaire had used as the data collection tool. According to Parahoo (2006), the quantitative method initiated from the idea that human phenomena and variables in human behavior had been studied objectively hence this method had carefully selected as a suitable research approach. Robson (2007) added that quantitative research uses a solid design that organizes in advance the research question and a comprehensive method for data collection and analysis.

3.2 Population and Sampling

3.2.1 Population

Parahoo (2006, p.258) defines the population as the total number of units from which data can potentially collect. Also, Copper and Schindler (2014) define the population as the total collection of elements about which the researcher intended to make inferences. Therefore, the current study interested in making judgments about third-year English Language students at Colleges of Education and Languages at Sudan University of science and technology.

3.2.2 Sampling

Proctor et al. (2010) define a sample as "*a proportion of a population*". Furthermore, Proctor et al. (2010), claims that, in quantitative research, the size of the sample should be calculated at the design stage According to (OECD, 2012), the sampling technique is the specific process through which the entities of the sample are selected. This study employed a simple random sampling technique to pick the study sample. Mugenda et al. (2012) define a random sampling technique as a method that gives elements through which a study population an equal chance of being sampled. A sample size comprises a group of respondents, consisting of part of the target population carefully selected to represent that population (Cooper and Schindler, 2014). For this reason, it is suggested to use a sample size of 100 English language learners at colleges of Education and languages in Sudan University of Science and Technology being selected as participants in the study. The participants will be selected using a simple random sampling method.

4. Results and Discussion

This section is mainly devoted to data analysis of the data collected through the questionnaire. The researcher obtains around (99) repossesses for the participants of the study. The collected data entered into (SPSS) for statistical treatment and producing the outputs to answer the main research question. Suitable statistical methods used to include the descriptive and inferential statistical methods.

The statistical analysis in this section will proceed to cover the assessment of the sample responses towards the questionnaire dimensions.

5. Results of Research Question

This part of data analysis is devoted to answer the following research questions.

5.1 Discussion of Q1: To what extent are university students motivated towards learning English language?

To provide answer to this research questions which aims to examine to what extent the university students motivated towards learning English language, the student's perceptions illustrated in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Participants perceptions regarding to what extent university students motivated to learn English language

Item No.		Mean	SD	Ranking
1	Learning English makes me more knowledgeable.	4.58	0.59	2
2	My parents will be proud if I can learn English well.	4.25	0.87	6
3	I will learn English even if it is not compulsory.	4.03	1.01	8
4	I will do my best to learn English.	4.58	0.59	3
5	I can travel around the world if I learn English well.	4.58	0.64	1
6	For me, a cultured person should learn English.	4.32	0.73	4
7	My colleagues encourage me to learn English.	4.17	0.80	7
8	Technological advancement motivates me to learn English.	4.30	0.86	5
	Overall mean value.	4.35	0.32	

Table 4.1 presents the students' perceptions of the current study regarding what extent University students were motivated to learn the English language. The results reveal that the overall mean value is reaching (4.35) with SD (0.32). Therefore, university students were highly motivated to learn the English language.

The detailed analysis of the most important motivators to learn the English language presented as follows: Table 4.1 showed that among the most important motivators for learning the English language according to the students' point of view is traveling around the world. This high response is supported by the mean value reaching (4.58) with SD (0.64). This means that the need to travel around the world is considered as the most important motivator for students to achieve various purposes such as pursuing higher education or entertainment or searching for jobs and business.

While the second motivator for students to learn the English language is related to knowledge, as the mean value equal to (4.58) with SD (0.59) indicates that. Therefore, we conclude that the majority of students strongly believe that, learning the English language makes them obtain more knowledge as they can be able to join and understand different cultures all over the world.

In addition to that, when students' participants of the current study provide their thought regarding statement 4 (i.e. I will do my best to learn English), the results reveal that the mean value is reaching (4.58) with SD (0.59). This mean value indicates that the majority of the students confirm that, they will do their best to learn the English language. Hence the high level of interest of students to learn the English language can be attributed for various reasons including better future, social position in the community, pursuing higher education.

When students' participants of the current studies determine their views in concern with the statement 6 (i.e. For me, a cultured person should learn English) the results in table 4.1 shows that the mean value is equal to (4.32) with SD (0.73). This high response indicates that almost all students believe that, a cultured person should learn English. This means that persons who have high skills in writing, speaking, and reading the English language can communicate with different cultures, and so they can acquire more knowledge in particular in the nowadays global society that influenced by technological and communication revolutions changes.

Furthermore, when participants of the current study, show their perceptions regarding statement 8 (i.e. Technological advancement motivates me to learn English), the results reveal that the mean value to the participant's responses is reaching (4.30) with SD (0.86). Thus, we conclude that the majority of students' subjects of the study strongly agreed that, technological advancement is regarded as among the most effective motivators to learn English.

While when students' subjects of the study, show their responses regarding the statement 2 (i.e. My parents will be proud if I can learn English well), the results in table 4.6, reveal that, the mean value towards this statement is equal to (4.25), with SD (0.87). Meaning that almost all students confirm that, their parents have an essential role to motivate them to learn the English language.

Whereas when participants of the current study present their views regarding the statement 7 (My colleagues encourage me to learn English), the results found that, the overall mean value is reaching (4.17) with SD (0.80). This mean value indicates that almost all students agree that, their colleagues have a positive role to encourage them to learn English.

Finally, when students provide their opinion regarding the statement 3 stated that (I will learn English even if it is not compulsory), the results found that, the overall mean value of students' responses is reaching (4.03) with SD (1.01). This indicates almost all students have their own decision to learn English even if it is not compulsory. So, we conclude that almost university students already decided to learn English, meaning that, they have conceived the importance of learning the English language to their future. Based on the analysis of students' perceptions regarding what extent they were motivated

to learn the English language, the results found that students were very highly motivated to learn the English language. There are many motivations that, influence the students, at the top of these motivation factors is that the need for traveling around the world, and the second motivator is that, almost students confirm that, learning English makes them more knowledgeable as they can be able to communicate, and know different cultures, and at the third level, students show the high level of interest to do their best to learn English. In addition to that, parents have a significant role to motivate students to learn the English language, besides that, almost all students believe that a cultured person should learn English.

4.2 Discussion of Q2: To what extent does the university students' background affect their motivation with regard English language learning?

Table 4.2: The effect of students' background on their attitudes and motivation with regard to English language learning

Item No	Statements	Mean	SD	Ranking
1	High level of competence in English will increase my chances of earning a good salary.	4.09	0.96	4
2	My parents often say that English is important for my future.	4.21	0.90	3
3	People around me believe that learning English is a waste of time.	2.33	1.19	6
4	Learning English is important as it is one of the requirements for high- education.	4.27	0.75	2
5	My financial situation hinders my learning of English.	2.87	1.02	5
6	Having a good English language teacher positively affects my attitude to learn English.	4.46	0.64	1
	Overall mean value.	3.71	0.37	

The results in table 4.2 shows the participants of the study perceptions, regarding the effect of student's background on their attitudes and motivation towards English language learning. the results reveal that, the overall mean value is reaching (3.71) with SD (0.37). Therefore, we conclude that, the majority of students have a high and positive background, which affect their attitudes and motivation towards English language learning.

Furthermore, the results found that, among the most important things that, show the positive background of students that, effect on their attitudes and motivation towards English language learning is that, the majority of participants strongly agree that, having a good English language teacher positively affects their attitudes to learn English. This high positive response is supported by the mean value (4.46) with SD (0.64). Therefore, the qualified, well educated, and well-trained teacher is the most important factor that motivate and affect positively on the students' attitudes to learning English language.

In addition to that, among the most important factors that influence highly and positively on the students' attitudes and motivate them to learn English language, is that, Learning English is important as it is one of the requirements for high- education. Therefore, almost participants strongly agree that, learning English is very important for

them, because it is considered as one of the requirements for high education as the mean value is equal to (4.27) with SD (0.75).

It is also noticed that, when participants of the study provide their perceptions regarding the statement No.2 (i.e. My parents often say that English is important for my future), The results in table 4.3, reveal that, the mean value is equal to (4.21) with SD (0.90). hence, this mean value indicates that, the majority of students strongly confirm their parents based on their experience often tell them that, English is important for their future, in particularly in the nowadays changing world.

While when students were being asked to show their responses regarding to the statement 1 (i.e. High level of competence in English will increase my chances of earning a good salary) the results in table 4.3, reveal that, the mean value to participants' perceptions is reaching (4.09) with SD (0.96). Therefore, almost participants agree that, high level of competence in English will increase the students' chances of earning a good salary. Therefore, high level of competence in English is one of the factors that have a positive effect on students' attitudes and motivation to learn English language, because of its relation with increasing the chances of the students to earn a good salary, when they being employed, meaning that it will improve the graduates' financial situations.

Whereas when the participants of the study were providing their perceptions regarding their views regarding the statement 6 (i.e. financial situation hinders my learning of English), the results found that, the mean value to participants responses is reaching (2.87) with SD (1.02). Meaning that, the students were sure if their financial situation hinders their learning English.

Finally, when participants of the study show their views regarding the statement 3 (i.e. People around me believe that learning English is a waste of time) the results in table 4.3, reveal that the mean value to participants' responses is equal to (2.33) with SD (1.19). This result indicates that most students do not agree that, people around them believe that learning English is a waste of time.

Therefore, based on the previous analysis, regarding the effect of students' background on their attitudes and motivation towards English language learning, the results found that many factors have a positive effect on students' attitudes and motivation to learn the English language. The most important ones include, having a good English language teacher positively affects their attitudes to learn English, and Learning English is important, as it is one of the requirements for high- education, in addition to that, parents have a supportive role to encourage students to learn the English language because it is important to their future.

4.3 Discussion of Q3: What are the possible factors which determine the reasons for learning the English language?

To understand the possible factors that determine the reasons for learning the English language, the students' participants of the study perceptions illustrated in table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Illustrates the possible factors determine the reasons for learning English

Item No		Mean	SD	Ranking
1	For me to communicate effectively in English is better than to get good grades in exams.	4.24	0.88	3
2	My main reason for choosing to study English is to improve my chances of finding a good job.	4.21	0.90	4
3	For me passing the exams of English is more important than my real communicative ability in the language.	2.13	1.11	6
4	I think that English learning is helpful for my future.	4.58	0.66	1
5	I have to learn English as it is one of the required courses.	4.20	0.73	5
6	Learning English helps me to find a remarkable position in my community.	4.40	0.74	2
	Overall mean value.	3.96	0.37	

The results in table 4.3 present the participants of the study perceptions, concerning the possible factors that determine the reasons for learning English. The results reveal that the overall mean value is reaching (3.96) with SD (0.37). Hence, we conclude that the majority of students believe that, many factors determine the reasons for learning the English language.

The detailed analysis of the possible factors that determine the reasons for learning the English language as follows:

The results in table 4.3 show that among the most important factors that determine the reasons for learning the English language is the helpfulness of English language learning for the students in their future, as the mean value is reaching (4.58) with SD 0.66. while the second most important factor that determines the reasons for learning English is that, learning English helps the students to find a remarkable position in the community, as the mean value is equal to (4.40) with SD (0.74).

Furthermore, the results in table 4.5, reveal that, when the student's participants of the current study show their views concerning the statement 4 (i.e. For me to communicate effectively in English is better than to get good grades in exams), it is clear that, the mean value to participants' perceptions is reaching (4.24) with SD 0.88. This mean value means the majority of students strongly agree that communicate effectively in English is better than getting good grades in exams.

While when the students subject of the study provide their views regarding the statement 2 (i.e. my main reason for choosing to study English is to improve my chances of finding a good job), the results in table 4.5, show that, the mean value to participants responses is reaching (4.21) with SD (0.90). The mean value confirms that the majority of students strongly agree that, their main reason for choosing to study English is to improve their chances of finding a good job. This indicates that almost all believe that, among the most important factors to learn the English language to improve their chances of a good job.

On the other hand, when students' participants of the study provide their views concerning statement 5 (i.e. I have to learn English, as it is one of the required courses) the results found that the mean value is reaching (4.21), with SD (0.73). thus, almost

students though they study the English language because it is a required course in the university.

Finally, when students present their views regarding the statement 3 (i.e. For me passing the exams of English is more important than my real communicative ability in the language) the results reveal that, the mean value to participants' perceptions is equal to (2.13) with SD (1.11). This mean value suggests that the majority of students do not agree that, passing the exams of the English language is more important than their real communicative ability in the language.

At the end of the analysis of the students' perceptions concerning the possible factors that determine the reasons for learning the English language. The results found that there are various possible factors that, determine the reasons for learning the English language. The most important factors encourage the students to pursue learning the English language include that, the majority of students strongly agreed that, English learning is helpful for them in their coming future, and almost all of them strongly confirm that learning English help them to find a reasonable position in the community.

In addition to that, almost all students strongly believe that, for them, the effective communication in English is better than to get good grades in exams, furthermore, almost of the students think that their main reason to choose to study English is to improve their chances of finding a good job. However, almost all students ignore that, passing exams of English is to have any importance than their real communicative ability in the language. That means they considered first to improve their real communicative ability in English language.

5. Findings and Recommendations

This section concludes the thesis by answering the research questions proposed at the beginning of the research. Then the discussion of the findings is presented and followed by a proposed recommendation that will provide great input regarding university students' motivation and English language learning. At the end of this section, the conclusion is drawn from this study. Also, this section provides a suggestion for further studies.

5.1 Findings

1. The results of the study confirmed that many factors have a positive effect on students' motivation to learn the English language. The most important ones include, having a good English language teacher positively affects their attitudes to learn English, and Learning English is important, as it is one of the requirements for high- education. Furthermore, the results of the study reveal that parents have a supportive role to encourage students to learn the English language because it is important to their future. In addition to that, a High level of competence in English has a positive effect by increasing the students' chances of earning a good salary in the future.

2. The results found that the most important factors that encourage students to pursue their learning are that learning English is helpful for them in the coming future. In addition to that, learning English helps the students to find a reasonable position in the community. Moreover, the results found that, among the most important factor that motivates and influence students to learn English, is that, students have a high level of likeness for learning English, the second factor is that, learning English is one of the most important for students' future life, and learning is interesting. In addition to that, learning English is fun, and the sound of the English language is attractive motivators.
3. The results found that students were very highly motivated to learn the English language. There are many factors, motivate the students, on top of the motivates factors is that, the need for traveling around the world, and the second motivator is that, almost all students confirm that, learning English makes them more knowledgeable as they can be able to communicate.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the finding's discussion of the study, the researcher recommends the following recommendations:

1. The findings indicated that the students have certain reasons for learning the language and hold significant attitudes toward the use of the English language that should be considered by English instructors and syllabus designers in preparing their materials, curriculum and teaching methods.
2. Teachers should encourage students to be active in the class by giving a chance to suggest or giving an opinion to solve problems in an experiment activity for instance.

References

- Cooper, D. R. & Schindler, P. S. (2014). *Business research methods*. New York: McGraw-Hill Companies.
- Cook, V. (2000). *Linguistics and second language acquisition*. Beijing: Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press and Macmillan Publishers Ltd.
- Ryan R. M. and Deci, E. L. (2000). Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations: Classic Definitions and New Directions. In *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25, 54–6.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2015). Motivation in second and foreign language learning. In *Language Teaching*, 31, 117
- Dörnyei, Z. (2014). *Motivating learners, motivating teachers: Building vision in the language classroom*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2015). *The psychology of the language learner revisited*. New York: Routledge.
- Ellis, Rod. (1994). *The Study of Second Language Acquisition*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. The study of second language acquisition. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press by Arrangement with Oxford University Press.

- Gardner, R. C. (2003). Integrative motivation and second language acquisition. Joint plenary talk at Canadian Association of Applied Linguistics/Canadian Linguistics Association, May.
- Gardner, R. C. (1985). *Social Psychology and Second Language Learning: The Role of Attitudes and Motivation*. London: Edward Arnold.
- Girard, D. (2005). Motivation: The Responsibility of the Teacher. *ELT Journal* 31.2, 97- 102
- Johnstone, K. (1999). *Research on language learning and teaching: 1997-1998*. Language Learning. London: Routledge.
- Crookes, G, & Schmidt, R. (1991). Motivation: Reopening the research agenda. *Language Learning*, 41 (4), 469-512. Deci, L.E., & Ryan, R.M.
- Krashen, S. (1985). *The Input Hypothesis: Issues and Implications*. New York: Longman.
- Lightbrown, P. M. & Spada N. (2001). Factors affecting second language learning. In: Candl in, C. N. & Mercer, N. (Eds.), *English language teaching in its social context*. London: Routledge.
- Mugenda et al (2012). *Research methods -Quantitative and Qualitative approaches*. xxxx
- OECD (2012). *Putting the Young in Business: Policy Challenges for Youth Entrepreneurship*. The LEED Program, Territorial Development Division, Paris.
- Masgoret, A. M., & Gardner, R. C., (2003). Attitudes, motivation and second Language learning: a meta-analysis of studies conducted by Gardner and associates. *Language Learning*, 53, 167–210.
- Parahoo, K. (2006). *Nursing research: principles, process and issues*, 2nd edn, Palgrave Macmillan, Houndsmill.
- Proctor S, Allan T. and Lacey A. (2010). Sampling. In *the Research Process in Nursing*, 6th edn. (Gerrish K. & Lacey A., eds), Wiley-Blackwell, Oxford.
- Pintrich, P. R. (2003). A motivational science perspective on the role of student motivation in learning and teaching contexts. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95, 667-686.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25, pp. 54-67.
- Robson C. (2007). *How to do a Research Project: a guide for undergraduate students*. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford.
- Schumann, John. (1986). An Acculturation Model for Second Language Acquisition. *Journal of Multilingual & Multicultural Development*. DO.10.1080/01434632.1986.9994254
- Walker, C., Greene, B., & Mansell, R. (2006). Identification with academics, intrinsic/extrinsic motivation, and self-efficacy as predictors of cognitive engagement. In *Learning and Individual Differences*, 16(1), pp. 1-12.

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